

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2024-05-24	Paul Zabel	Initial document setup.
0.2	2024-05-24	Henning Wache	Content insertion
0.3	2024-06-03	Henning Wache, Noria Brecher, Rachele Perelli	Content insertion, references and corrections
0.5	2024-07-04	Luca Kiewiet, Mateo Rejon Lopez, Paul Zabel	Added chapter 4.
1.0	2024-07-06	Paul Zabel	Final formatting.

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1 Introduction

This document describes the efforts of the LUXWEX projects towards the development of simulants, both for the extraction process and the purification process. There are two different simulant products prepared for these ends. The purpose of the simulants is to be as close as possible to their real counterparts, namely the icy lunar regolith, and the liquid water after the ice is extracted from this icy regolith. A good simulant will result in more accurate and more useful results. In chapter 2 of this document, the development and end product of this liquid water is explained. This liquid water is contaminated with regolith dust particles and other volatiles, in line with the current state of knowledge on volatiles on the Moon. The use of this Lunar raw water simulant is to test the purification system of the project. In Chapter 3, the development of the ice particles is explained. These ice particles will be later mixed with the lunar regolith simulant. In Chapter 4, the development of the icy lunar regolith simulant is explained. Multiple methods of mixing the regolith simulant with the ice are explained, and a conclusion about the best method for the project is chosen.

NOTE: The document D4.4 (this document) serves as a report on the development process of the lunar raw water simulant (D4.2) and the lunar water ice simulant (D4.3).

D4.2 and D4.3 are classified as 'OTHER' and are considered similar to class 'DEM' deliverables, but being consumables rather than hardware.

2 Development of the Lunar Raw Water Simulant

2.1 Purpose of the raw water simulant

Lunar raw water simulant is designed to mimic the chemical composition, physical properties, and behavior of lunar water ice that may exist on the Moon. The simulant is carefully formulated to accurately represent the unique characteristics of water found in lunar regolith, including its potential impurities, mineral content, and distribution within the soil.

By utilizing lunar raw water simulants, scientists can conduct experiments and develop technologies that are specifically tailored to extract, purify, and use water resources on the lunar surface. Understanding the behavior and properties of lunar water is crucial for future lunar missions and potential efforts of establishing a sustainable presence on the Moon.

The simulant is used in the development of technologies for water extraction, purification, storage, and utilization for life support systems, propellant production, agriculture, and other applications.

2.2 Selection of contaminants

The information available about the composition of lunar water comes from the Lunar Crater Observation and Sensing Satellite (LCROSS) missions.

The lunar raw water simulant is designed to include volatiles detected by the LCROSS mission and lunar regolith particles.

2.2.1 Volatiles

The raw water simulant used for testing purposes cannot contain all the volatiles detected by LCROSS mission.

Table 2-1 summarizes the compounds detected by the LCROSS mission and the reasons for not considering the compound for the lunar raw water simulant.

The reasons can be classified as follows:

- A high safety risk for the laboratory staff.
- Lack of laboratory infrastructure to add gases to the raw water simulant in reproducible and defined concentrations.
- The compound is expected to remain in the gas phase throughout the process.

For lunar raw water simulant preparation, compounds marked with a ✓ are selected.

Table 2-1: Selection of volatiles for the lunar raw water simulant.

Compound		LCROSS reported abundance with respect to detected water in mol _x /mol _{H₂O} (Colaprete et al. (2010), Gladstone et al. (2010) & Holquist et al. (2021))	Selection for lunar raw water simulant
Hydrogen sulfide	H ₂ S	0.073	a), b)
Ammonia	NH ₃	0.027	✓
Sulfur dioxide	SO ₂	0.014	✓
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	0.014	b)
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	0.009	✓
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	0.007	✓
Methane	CH ₄	0.003	b)
Hydrogen	H ₂	0.023	c)
Carbon Monoxide	CO	0.081	a)

2.2.2 Particulates

Water extracted on the lunar surface may contain particulate impurities, as reported in the In-Situ Resource Utilization Gap Assessment Report (ISECG, 2021) and the Dust Mitigation Gap Assessment Report (ISECG, 2016). Therefore, the Lunar Highland Dust Simulant (LHS-1D) from Exolith Lab (Orlando, USA) is added to the lunar raw water simulant. This simulant provides a representative chemical composition of the Apollo 16 samples and a particle size range from <0.04 to 35 μm.

2.3 Preparation of lunar raw water simulant

In summary, the raw water simulant is prepared by dissolving dusty lunar regolith simulant and contaminants detected by LCROSS in ultrapure water. The composition depends on the different subsystem level tests of the water purification system as planned in the test campaign described in deliverable in D3.4 – Water Purification and Storage Design Report.

2.3.1 Calculation of volatile concentrations

The LCROSS mission data refers to icy water directly on moon surface. The extraction and capturing process impacts on the concentration of the volatiles present in liquid raw water. The volatile concentrations in the lunar raw water simulant are based on the concentrations reported by Holquist et al. (2021). The concentrations of the compounds in the water are assumed to be those reported by Holquist et al. (2021) (Table 7) for worst case cold trap performance. The concentrations are converted as follows (Eq.1) from the concentrations reported in ppb by Holquist et al. (2021), assuming a water density of 1000 g·L⁻¹:

$$C_{mg \cdot L^{-1}} = \frac{C_{ppb} \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot M_x}{M_{H_2O}} \cdot 1000 \frac{g}{L} \cdot 1000 \frac{mg}{g} \quad (1)$$

where $C_{mg \cdot L^{-1}}$ is the concentration in milligrams per litre, C_{ppb} is the concentration in parts per billion, M_x is the molar mass of the compound and M_{H_2O} is the molar mass of water. The concentrations of the selected compounds in milligrams per liter are given in Table 2-2. CO₂ to the lunar raw water simulant is not added because the reported CO₂ concentration after the cold trap is close to the CO₂ concentration of the dissolved CO₂ from the atmosphere in the water.

Table 2-2: Volatile concentrations in lunar raw water simulant.

Compound		Holquist et al. (2021), Worst Case
		mg · L ⁻¹
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	2.66E+00
Ammonia	NH ₃	8.79E-01
Sulfur dioxide	SO ₂	7.83E-02

2.3.2 Preparation of the stock solution

The lunar raw water simulant is prepared as a stock solution at the DLR and then diluted by TASI for the water purification subsystem tests. A total of eight different lunar raw water compositions will be used for the subsystem tests with two compositions not containing compounds detected by LCROSS. Each test is performed three times with a volume of 2 L of lunar raw water simulant, i.e. 6 L of lunar raw water per composition. A volume of 250 mL stock solution is provided to prepare 6 L of lunar raw water simulant.

2.3.2.1 Material

The following chemicals are used for the stock solution:

- Methanol: ROTIDRY®Sept ≥99,9 % (≤50 ppm H₂O), carlroth.com Best.-Nr. 5181.1
- Ammonia solution: 4 mol·L⁻¹ - 4 N, volumetric standard solution, carlroth.com Best.-Nr. 9897.1
- Sulphurous acid: ~6 % SO₂ in H₂O, carlroth.com Best.-Nr. 9328.1
- Ultrapure water with a resistivity of 18 MΩcm (ROTISOLV HPLC Gradient Grade)

2.3.2.2 Procedure

Table 2-3 gives the volume of the three compounds to prepare 250 mL of stock solution for 6 L of lunar raw water.

Table 2-3: Calculated volumes for preparing 250 mL stock solution for 6 L of lunar raw water.

250 mL stock solution for 6 L lunar raw water	CH ₃ OH >99.9%		NH ₃ 4 mol·L ⁻¹		SO ₂ ~6 % SO ₂	
	mg	μL	mg	μL	mg	μL
C3	15.97	20.17				
C4					0.47	9.73
C5			5.28	77.42		
C6			5.28	77.42	0.47	9.73
C7	15.97	20.17	5.28	77.42	0.47	9.73
C8	15.97	20.17	5.28	77.42	0.47	9.73

The volumes of the three compounds are calculated as follows:

Methanol with a density of 791.7 mg·mL⁻¹ at 20 °C

$$V_{CH_3OH} = \frac{2.66 \frac{mg}{L} \cdot 6L}{791.7 \frac{mg}{mL}} \cdot 10^3 \frac{\mu L}{mL} = 20.17 \mu L \quad (2)$$

Ammonia with a molar weight of 17.04 g·mol⁻¹

$$V_{NH_3} = \frac{0.879 \frac{mg}{L} \cdot 6L}{17.04 \cdot 10^3 \frac{mg}{mol}} \cdot (4 \frac{mol}{L})^{-1} \cdot 10^6 \frac{\mu L}{L} = 77.42 \mu L \quad (3)$$

Sulfur Dioxide with a molar weight of 64.06 g·mol⁻¹, solution density of 1.03 g·L⁻¹ at 20 °C and a molar weight SO₂·H₂O of 82.02 g·mol⁻¹

$$V_{SO_2} = \frac{0.0783 \frac{mg}{L} \cdot 6L \cdot (64.06 \cdot 10^3 \frac{mg}{mol})^{-1}}{1.03 \frac{g}{mL} \cdot (82.02 \frac{g}{mol})^{-1} \cdot 0.06} \cdot 10^3 \frac{\mu L}{mL} = 9.73 \mu L \quad (4)$$

The solution is prepared in a 250 mL volumetric flask. First, approximately 100 mL of ultrapure water is added to the volumetric flask and then the calculated volume of the methanol, ammonia and sulfur dioxide solution is added with a microliter pipette. The volumetric flask is then filled to just below the marked line with ultrapure water and gently shaken. Then, ultrapure water is added drop by drop until the base of the meniscus is level with the marked line. Finally, the volumetric flask is stoppered and the solution is mixed by inverting and swirling.

2.3.2.3 Storage of solutions

The solution is stored in HDPE bottles in a refrigerator for no longer than 6 months.

2.3.3 Preparation of solution for water purification tests

To prepare 2 L of lunar raw water for the water purification subsystem tests, the 250 mL stock solution is filled into a 6 L container and then filled to the 6 L mark with ultrapure water. The 6 L solution is then divided into three 2 L portions. As a final step in lunar raw water preparation, when needed, 1 g of LHS-1D is added to the solution and stirred gently for 3 hours.

2.4 Work Safety

The stock solution has to be prepared in a fume hood wearing protective gloves, glasses and a laboratory coat. For further information see the safety data sheet of the regolith simulant in the appendix.

Table 2-4 shows the concentrations of the three volatiles in the lunar raw water simulant compared to the dangerous goods regulations.

Table 2-4: Comparison of volatile concentrations in lunar raw water simulant to dangerous goods regulations.

	Hazard statement	Final concentration in 250 mL	H301	H311	H331	H370	H314	H318	H335	H332
Methanol	H301, H311, H331, H370, (H225)	0,00805 %	<4,5 %	<15 %	<3,5 %	<1 %	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Ammonia	H314, H318, H335, (H412)	0,00023 %	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	<1 %	<1 %	<20 %	n.a.
Sulphurous acid	H332, H314, H318	0,00211 %	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	<1 %	<1 %	n.a.	<22,5 %

3 Lunar Water Ice Simulant

3.1 Purpose of the water ice simulant

While the presence of water on the lunar surface is certain, the exact morphology and distribution are unknown. Here, micro-granular water ice particles are used as one possible shape of ice on the lunar surface. These particles are mixed with a regolith simulant to create an icy regolith simulant (see Section 4) but are also used independently for testing purposes and experiments.

This section describes the production, desiccation and storage of these water ice particles as well as their properties. To more closely resemble the material found on the lunar surface, the addition of other volatiles to the water ice that were found in the LCROSS ejecta plume is explained in Section 3.6.

3.2 Production of μm -sized granular water ice

To produce μm -sized water ice particles, a pre-existing ice machine is utilized. The working principle of this ice machine is to abruptly freeze a fine mist of water droplets in liquid nitrogen (Kreuzig, et al., 2023).

As can be seen in Figure 3-1, demineralized water inside a 24L aquarium (b) is vaporized by a piezo water atomizer (a), creating a fine mist of μm -sized water droplets. The size of these droplets depends on the piezo element's properties. The created mist of water droplets is then transported through a U-shaped tube (c) with the help of nitrogen as carrier gas. Upon impact into a liquid nitrogen filled Dewar (d), the water droplets are quenched (frozen abruptly), creating μm -sized granular water ice particles. The production rate of this machine is roughly 150 g/h. There are two machines available.

The machine is mostly automated, meaning that the liquid nitrogen in the Dewar is automatically refilled and the nitrogen carrier gas is constantly flowing through the tube after starting the machine. Only the nitrogen supply has to be taken care of by connecting the liquid and gas phase of a nitrogen can to the machine, and the demineralised water has to be refilled manually.

Figure 3-1: CAD drawing of the ice machine used to produce granular ice particles. A piezo water atomizer (a) inside a 24L aquarium (b) creates a fine mist of water droplets that are transported with the help of a nitrogen carrier gas through a tube (c) into a dewar (d) filled with liquid nitrogen and frozen there to create μm -sized granular ice particles (Kreuzig, et al., 2023).

3.3 Desiccation

The water ice particles produced by the ice machine are suspended in liquid nitrogen. To enable a precise mass determination and to prepare tests where ice is needed in a dry form, the liquid nitrogen is removed utilizing a desiccator.

This desiccator, which can be seen in Figure 3-2, consists of a stainless-steel tube that is cooled constantly to temperatures below 110K with a liquid nitrogen supply running through copper tubes around the system. Inside, the suspension of ice particles and liquid nitrogen can be stirred and pumped continuously, removing all liquid nitrogen over time without altering the particles themselves. Approximately 800 g of granular water ice can be desiccated at a time.

Figure 3-2: CAD drawing of the desiccator used to remove liquid nitrogen from freshly produced ice (Kreuzig, et al., 2023).

3.4 Properties of the ice particles

After desiccation, the resulting material is a fine powder of ice particles, in appearance similar to powdered sugar as displayed in Figure 3-4. On a microscopic level, these particles are of spherical shape as shown by the cryogenic scanning electron microscope (Cryo-SEM) image in Figure 3-3 and exhibit a well-defined size distribution with a median radius of $(2.4 \pm 0.1) \mu\text{m}$.

It should be noted that the desiccated ice particles exhibit strong adhesive forces, which means that if moved, they tend to clump together in agglomerates of up to multiple mm in size. This hinders the goal of producing a homogeneous mixture of water ice particles and regolith simulant later on. However, the desiccation process is necessary to determine the exact mass of the water ice sample. Without desiccation, the ice content of an icy regolith batch can only be subsequently measured by taking small samples and drying them. This leads to a larger uncertainty in comparison to the usage of desiccated ice particles for the estimation of the total batch ice content.

Figure 3-4: Desiccated water ice particles in a 125 mm diameter bowl. Ice agglomerates of up to a few mm in size are visible.

Figure 3-3: Cryo-SEM image of desiccated water ice particles with spherical shape (Kreuzig, et al., 2023).

3.5 Storage

The liquid nitrogen-ice suspension produced by the ice machine as well as the desiccated ice can be stored over the timespan of multiple days. Generally, the temperature of the ice stays below 110 K over the whole timespan of production and storage to sustain its morphology.

3.5.1 Storage of liquid nitrogen-ice suspension

The liquid nitrogen-ice suspension as produced by the ice machine can be stored in the same Dewar directly. After approximately one night, the liquid nitrogen has to be refilled. The morphology of the ice does not change since the particles are constantly suspended in liquid nitrogen. Up to a few hundred grams of ice particles can be stored in this way in either of the two Dewars available.

During production and storage, some frost might form on the upper edges of the Dewar and inside the tube of the ice machine which can fall into the Dewar. Thus, before using the suspension for experiments or desiccation, it is poured through a sieve to filter out any larger ice chunks.

3.5.2 Storage of desiccated ice

If desiccated, the ice particles can be stored in a cryogenic storage can. The storage can consist of a volume soaked with liquid nitrogen and a separate metal tube inside. Approximately 300 g of ice particles can be

filled into this tube. With two transport cans available, 600 g can be stored at a time. The liquid nitrogen in the cans should be refilled every few days to sustain a cryogenic environment over longer periods of time.

Additionally, the desiccated ice can be stored inside the desiccator itself after drying. As long as the liquid nitrogen supply is secured, the ice particles will sustain their morphology over multiple days.

3.6 Volatile concentrations for the preparation of the lunar ice simulant

Table 3-1 summarizes the compounds detected by the LCROSS mission and the reasons for not considering the compound for the lunar ice simulant. The reasons can be classified as follows:

- a) A high safety risk for the laboratory staff.
- b) Lack of laboratory infrastructure to add gases to the raw water simulant in reproducible and defined concentrations.
- c) The compound is expected to remain in the gas phase throughout the process.
- d) Degradation of the TVAC.

For the preparation of the lunar ice simulant, compounds marked with a ✓ are selected.

Table 3-1: Selection of volatiles for the lunar ice simulant.

Compound		LCROSS reported abundance with respect to detected water in mol _x /mol _{H₂O} [Colaprete, 2010, Gladstone 2010 & Holquist, 2020]	Selection lunar ice simulant
Hydrogen sulfide	H ₂ S	0.073	b) d)
Ammonia	NH ₃	0.027	d)
Sulfur dioxide	SO ₂	0.014	d)
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	0.014	b)
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	0.009	✓
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	0.007	✓
Methane	CH ₄	0.003	b)
Hydrogen	H ₂	0.023	c)
Carbon Monoxide	CO	0.081	a)

The concentrations are converted from Table 3-1 mol_x/mol_{H₂O} to g · L⁻¹ using the following formula:

$$C_{g \cdot L^{-1}} = \frac{C_{\text{mol}_x/\text{mol}_{H_2O}} \cdot M_x}{M_{H_2O}} \cdot 1000 \frac{g}{L} \tag{5}$$

where $C_{g \cdot L^{-1}}$ is the concentration in grams per litre, $C_{\text{mol}_x/\text{mol}_{H_2O}}$ is the concentration in moles of compound x per mole of water, M_x is the molar mass of the compound x and M_{H_2O} is the molar mass of water.

Table 3-2 gives the volume of CH₃OH (<99.9%, density(20°C): 0.7917 g·mL⁻¹) to prepare 25 L of water for the preparation of the lunar ice simulant.

Table 3-2: Volumes of compound added to the lunar ice simulant.

Compound		g · L ⁻¹		for 25 L
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	22.98	added as a solid	
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	11.93	15.07 ml·L ⁻¹	377 mL

$$V_{CH_3OH} = \frac{11.93 \frac{g}{L} \cdot 25L}{0.7917 \frac{g}{mL}} = 377 \text{ mL} \quad (6)$$

To create an ice simulant with Methanol, the water-soluble volatile can be added directly to the demineralized water in the ice machine. The sample can then be desiccated.

CO₂ on the contrary is added in a dry form (Kreuzig, et al., 2023). To produce CO₂ ice, liquid CO₂ is released under high pressure through a narrow nozzle, freezing the volatile instantly and capturing it in an isolated Styrofoam box. This process takes only a few seconds. The resulting CO₂ ice can then be weighed and added to the desiccated water ice particles in any ratio. Figure 3-5 shows a Cryo-SEM image of a mixture of water ice particles with CO₂ ice in a ratio of 3:1. The CO₂ ice particles are much larger in size and quite angular but can be intermixed with the water ice particles in a homogeneous way. Their median effective radius was determined to be $(6.7 \pm 0.5) \mu\text{m}$ (Kreuzig, et al., 2023).

Figure 3-5: Cryo-SEM image of a water-ice and CO₂-ice particle mixture in the ratio of 3:1 (Kreuzig, et al., 2023).

4 Development of the Icy-Regolith Simulant

4.1 Purpose of the simulant

The aim is to provide a micro-granular unfused icy-regolith simulant that resembles the material expected at permanently shadowed regions on the lunar surface, where volatiles such as water are proven to be existent (Colaprete, et al., 2010). The baseline of these experiments as derived from the LCROSS ejecta plume is $5.6 \pm 2.9\%$ of water ice by weight with the addition of CO₂ and Methanol as explained in Section 3.6 of this document.

In literature, multiple ways of creating an icy regolith simulant are already established (Ricardo, et al., 2023). Instead of freezing wet regolith or depositing water vapor on the regolith, a two-component approach is utilized here where premade micro-granular water ice particles are intermixed with a precooled regolith simulant. The resulting material is expected to reflect a homogeneous distribution of ice particles in a bed of regolith grains. Such a material is a possible outcome of the constant micrometeorite bombardment on the lunar surface.

Since the thermal conductivity of such a discretely and homogeneously distributed icy material is expected to be minimal in comparison to fused or embedded ice in regolith as well as in comparison to samples with much larger sized ice grains, this icy-regolith simulant provides a worst-case scenario in terms of extraction efficiency for a given water content and if successful, can provide a prove of concept for thermal energy-based water extraction systems.

To create such an icy-regolith simulant, the water ice particles and the regolith simulant must first be prepared as described in Sections 4.3 and 4.4 and then mixed. Section 4.5 summarizes multiple methods of mixing tested on small-scale samples to evaluate the behaviour of the material, while Section 4.6 describes a first test on a larger 15 kg batch done to practise the procedure developed for the extraction experiments. Section 4.7 then describes a large batch production test done with a dry mix approach while Section 4.8 goes into detail on how the final product is handled around the vacuum chamber and during the filling process, specifically to ensure the simulant is not contaminated in any way during this last step before the extraction experiment can start.

4.2 Safety precautions

When handling any regolith simulants, respiratory protection in the form of a FFP3 mask has to be used and processing should be done in well-ventilated environments only. Most simulants contain silica dust, which is classified as a human carcinogen.

In addition to that, eye protection and skin protection in the form of gloves and a dust suit or lab coat should be used. If exposed, skin should be washed thoroughly.

The simulant is not to be consumed and neither should anything else be consumed in the presence of the regolith simulant.

While handling liquid nitrogen and any cryogenic materials, safety gloves approved for cryogenic temperatures and eye protection should be used. Liquid nitrogen is easily adsorbed by clothing if spilled and can damage skin underneath. Extremely low temperature materials often do not seem cold but are able to damage skin on the touch.

Evaporating liquid nitrogen will multiply in volume and should therefore be used in well-ventilated environments only. If not, oxygen levels might drop quickly which can lead to fainting and death. Liquid nitrogen may never be placed in a closed container without pressure regulation as there is a risk of explosion.

Additionally, when combining liquid nitrogen and dusts, liquid nitrogen should not be added to warm materials directly since fine dust particles will explosively evaporate with the nitrogen on contact. Samples should therefore be precooled beforehand.

4.3 Water ice particles

The water ice particles used to create a micro-granular sample are of spherical shape with a median radius of 2.4 µm. The production process of these particles is explained in Section 3 of this document.

For the creation of an icy regolith simulant, the ice particles are used either suspended in liquid nitrogen (wet mix) or in a desiccated state (dry mix), which leads to different results in terms of homogeneity further elaborated on in Section 4.5.

4.4 Lunar regolith simulant

The lunar regolith simulant used here is a commercially available product by Lunex Technologies. This section presents the properties of this simulant as well as the steps needed to prepare it for the mixing process to create the icy-regolith simulant.

4.4.1 Properties

The lunar regolith simulant is made from a mixture of 75% anorthosite (TUBS-T) and 25% basalt (LX-M), resembling the bedrock of the terrae and mare regions of the lunar surface near the south pole where water ice is expected to be present.

It has a granular form with highly angular particles, resulting in a bulk density of 1.24 g/cm³ with a particle size distribution in the range of < 0.01 – 1 mm. Approximately 50 % of the total weight is distributed among the smallest particles < 50 µm. The simulant’s chemical and mineral composition are elaborated in Table 4-1 and Table 4-2, respectively.

Table 4-1: Regolith simulant chemical composition as oxide sum

Component	Weight %
SiO ₂	48.7
TiO ₂	0.7
Al ₂ O ₃	26.1
FeO	3.3
MgO	2.6
CaO	13.0
Na ₂ O	3.2
K ₂ O	0.6
MnO	0.1
Cr ₂ O ₃	< 0.1
P ₂ O ₅	0.1

Table 4-2: Regolith simulant mineral composition

Mineral phase	Vol %
Plagioclase feldspar (Labradorite)	9.6
Plagioclase feldspar (Bytownite)	72.75
Pyroxene (Augite)	10.48
Olivine (Forsterite)	4.6
Titanomagnetite	0.25
Alkali Feldspar	0.08

4.4.2 Preparation technique

To prepare the simulant for the mixing process with ice, there a several steps needed to ensure a reproducible process and resulting material properties. This section describes how to dry, store and precool the regolith simulant.

4.4.2.1 Drying regolith simulant

The regolith simulant is stored in air-tight plastic containers in batches of 15 kg. During production and storage, small amounts of humidity are adsorbed by the material over time. To receive a well-determined mor-

phology and amount of water ice in the final icy simulant, as much residual water as possible has to be removed from the stored regolith before mixing with ice without changing the simulant's properties. In laboratory stable conditions, the water content is typically < 0.5 wt. %. By heating the simulant in an oven at 110°C for at least 12 hours, physically adsorbed (non-bound) water is removed (NASA-STD-1008, 2021). This procedure was also counterchecked with a vacuum drying oven, where no additional water could be removed from the previously dried samples. The bound water content is < 0.01 wt. % directly after drying.

4.4.2.2 Storing dried regolith simulant

After drying, the regolith simulant has to be stored in a humidity-free environment to avoid additional water adsorption which can happen in a matter of minutes. A vacuum-grade stainless steel CF-200 tube is used for this purpose. With a diameter of 200 mm and a length of 406 mm, it is capable of storing up to 15.8 kg of the here-used regolith simulant with a bulk density of 1.24 g/cm^3 .

The regolith simulant is inserted promptly after drying. The filled CF tube (see Figure 4-1) is then sealed with the top flange. A copper gasket provides a tight seal. In this environment, the dry regolith simulant can be stored over the span of multiple days without any significant increase in water content.

Figure 4-1: CF tube filled with dried regolith. The tube is 200 mm wide and 406 mm long.

For reopening the flange to fill in more regolith at a later time, the entire setup is placed in a dry environment (e. g. box filled with N_2) to avoid water adsorption from air humidity. Upon opening, the time of refilling is minimized while also pouring in the dry simulant carefully and slowly to prevent the finest dust particles from leaving the sample. The copper gasket is then cleaned thoroughly each time to remove the fine lunar dust particles and to provide a tight seal.

4.4.2.3 Precooling dried regolith simulant

The dried regolith simulant is precooled using liquid nitrogen. It is important that liquid nitrogen is not added directly into non-precooled regolith due to the finest dust particles getting airborne easily with the abruptly evaporating N_2 gas. This is why the precooling process is also done with the CF tube. The closed stainless-steel tube with approximately 15kg of regolith simulant is submerged into a liquid nitrogen bath, which is shown in Figure 4-2. Cooling the tube takes multiple hours due to the low thermal conductivity of stainless steel and the regolith simulant inside. After a night of cooling, the inner material is below 100 K. During this time the liquid nitrogen bath is refilled automatically to constantly cool the sample throughout the night. After cooling, the CF tube should be handled in dry atmospheres only and transportation times outside of those should be kept to a minimum to limit frost formation. The material should be used immediately since the sample heats up after removal from the liquid nitrogen bath.

Figure 4-2: CF tube submerged in liquid nitrogen. The top flange in this image is not screwed tight yet to enable the measurement of the temperature inside with a Pt-1000 sensor.

4.5 Small-scale development and testing

The tests presented in this section are done on small batches of up to a few hundred grams of mass each to find a good approach of producing a homogeneous sample. The insights found here are later applied to produce a larger batch for the LUXEX extraction experiments in the next chapter.

The homogeneity of the test samples is qualitatively analysed by visual appearance only. More rigorous methods such as Cryo-SEM imaging or other scans might be of interest to determine the exact morphology of the ice particles present in the future.

All processing steps listed in this section were done in a dry atmosphere of gaseous nitrogen inside of a glovebox to prevent frost formation from air humidity. Tools used were precooled and kept inside the dry environment at all times.

It is important to note that the small batch testing was done with a different regolith simulant than described in Section 4.4.1, namely LHS-1 by Exolith Lab. This is due to a change of simulant provider during the project. The chemical composition of these simulants is quite similar though, only the particle size distribution varies slightly, which should not affect the production setup significantly. Details on the properties of LHS-1 can be found in the appendix of this document.

4.5.1 Using desiccated water ice particles

The largest advantage of using desiccated water ice particles is the precise determination of the water mass present in the sample. The ice particles extracted from the desiccator or storage cans can be poured into a precooled bowl and then weighed with a scale.

The regolith simulant is weighed as well and put inside a bowl which sits inside a bath of liquid nitrogen. The regolith is precooled completely before any mixing is done.

4.5.1.1 Mixing without liquid nitrogen

Without any liquid nitrogen inside the sample, the desiccated ice particles are added to the precooled regolith simulant directly and stirred with a spoon. Due to the ice particles exhibiting strong adhesive forces when desiccated, the micro-meter sized ice particles bond together to form agglomerates. The agglomerates are also visible in the icy-regolith sample as depicted in Figure 4-3. While stirring, these agglomerates can be broken down with a spoon and some applied force but the exact shape of the ice is unknown then. Most likely, the particles are not discretely distributed but still in heaps of many bound particles. The process of manually crushing the agglomerates is not applicable to large batch samples since it takes too much time and

effort. The number and size of the clumps can be reduced by carefully adding small amounts of ice into the regolith at a time and stirring slowly, making sure to not to compact the ice more than it was initially.

Figure 4-3: Desiccated ice particles intermixed with a dry regolith simulant creating up to 3 mm sized agglomerates.

4.5.1.2 Mixing with liquid nitrogen

The components can also be mixed with the addition of liquid nitrogen. Initially, the ice is poured into the regolith simulant as in the previous step. Additionally, liquid nitrogen is added until a muddy consistency is reached. With a precooled spoon, the material is then stirred to combine. Figure 4-4 shows the resulting icy sample. The addition of liquid nitrogen to the dry mixture did not influence the result in any significant way and ice agglomerates were still present in the sample. However, the stirring process is easier when liquid nitrogen is added to the sample.

4.5.1.3 Mixing with liquid nitrogen and whisking

To break the ice agglomerates in an automated way, a whisk attachment was put on a power tool to stir the material. With a sample prepared in the same way as described in the previous section, no significant improvement in homogeneity could be observed since the ice agglomerates could not be broken down so easily.

Figure 4-4: Whisking the icy regolith sample. No significant effect on the apparent number or size of the ice agglomerates can be seen.

Figure 4-5: Water ice particles intermixed with the regolith simulant and added liquid nitrogen. Agglomerates are present in numerous sizes up to a few millimetres and very visible due them floating on top of the liquid nitrogen.

4.5.1.4 Suspending the ice agglomerates first in liquid nitrogen

It was also tested to pour the desiccated ice particles into liquid nitrogen to try and dissolve the agglomerates back into discrete micro-meter sized particles. For this process, the mass of the ice is measured after desiccation, the ice agglomerates are then stirred with liquid nitrogen and afterwards, the resulting suspension is mixed into a precooled regolith simulant sample.

In the liquid nitrogen ice-suspension, some of the agglomerates can be broken down into smaller chunks as visible in Figure 4-6. While some of the agglomerates are broken up during this process, many are still present afterwards. Sieving this slurry into the regolith simulant could then remove the chunks, although the mass loss has to be considered. In addition, the real size of the remaining ice particles is not known at this point and could be any value below the sieve size used.

4.5.1.5 Sieving the ice before mixing

By sieving the ice particles before adding them to the regolith simulant, the size of the agglomerates can be controlled with the sieve size as an upper boundary. In this way, a more homogeneous sample can be created even with agglomerates of ice.

With this method, there might be some losses of ice mass due to material being stuck to the sieve. This has to be considered and measured to keep the advantage of a precise mass retained.

The sieving process can be done with any sieve size. However, it is not feasible to sieve large amounts of ice through small sieve sizes (< 500 μm). The larger the sieve opening, the faster the process is. Figure 4-8 shows the results of sieving desiccated ice onto the regolith simulant with different sieve sizes of 250 μm and 1 mm.

In conclusion, the use of desiccated water ice particles enables the exact determination of the mass of water present in the sample. At the same time, the agglomeration of the ice particles mostly prevents the creation of a homogeneous micro-granular icy-regolith simulant.

Figure 4-6: Suspension of liquid nitrogen and desiccated water ice particles. Some agglomerates are still present after stirring.

Figure 4-7: Desiccated ice particles sieved onto regolith simulant samples. In comparison to the uncontrolled millimetre-sized agglomerates (left bottom), the sieved agglomerates can be made much smaller depending on the sieve size (left 250 μ , right 1 mm).

4.5.2 Using liquid nitrogen-suspended ice particles

Another approach to creating an icy-regolith simulant is to use the liquid nitrogen slush with ice particles as freshly produced by the ice machine described in Section 3.2. With this approach, the precise mass of the ice put into the sample cannot be determined, since the amount of liquid nitrogen in the Dewar varies strongly due to constant evaporation. However, it is possible to retrieve a measure of the water ice content by drying samples of the mixed batch after the mixing process and measuring the removed mass.

To create an icy-regolith simulant sample, the precooled regolith simulant is first mixed with liquid nitrogen as shown in Figure 4-9 to create a base slurry that can be stirred afterwards.

Figure 4-8: Liquid nitrogen added to the regolith simulant creating a mud like material. A regular table spoon is used to mix the small sample.

The fresh liquid nitrogen-ice suspension is then poured through a sieve into the muddy simulant. This way, larger chunks created by frost during the production in the ice machine are removed and only the micrometre-sized particles remain. The ice suspension not yet mixed with the regolith is shown in Figure 4-10 together with a close-up.

The resulting mixture can then be easily stirred to produce an icy-regolith simulant. After a lot of stirring and letting the liquid nitrogen boil off, no trace of any larger agglomerates is visible as depicted in Figure 4-11.

By taking a few smaller samples of the order of 20 g, the water content was determined by weight loss in a vacuum drying oven at 110°C for 12 hours to be at approximately (2.9 ± 0.1) wt. %.

In summary, this approach of mixing provides a visually well-mixed homogeneous sample, where the ice particles can be expected to be in a discrete form without much agglomeration. On the downside, this method is not suitable for achieving a precisely predefined water ice content.

By using the approximate production rate of the ice machine, an estimate on the amount of ice put into a larger icy-regolith simulant batch can be derived from the run time of the machine. However, this estimation is highly error prone, since the manually controlled parameters of the ice machine as well as frost formation during the process can influence the resulting amount of ice in a great deal.

Figure 4-9: Liquid nitrogen ice-suspension poured into a mixture of regolith simulant and liquid nitrogen. The width of the container shown (left) is approximately 20 cm. The right image shows a 3 cm close-up of the same mixture.

Figure 4-10: Mixed icy-regolith sample with an ice content of 2.9 wt. %. The image shows a 5 cm frame. There is no visible trace of the individual water ice particles or any larger ice agglomerates. Most of the liquid nitrogen boiled off, which is why the material seems almost dry.

4.6 Large batch production test - wet mixing

For LUWEX an upper mass of 15 kg is required for the icy regolith sample. For this purpose, the procedures from the development and testing phases must be scaled up. This section summarizes the first large batch icy-regolith simulant production approach and the lessons learned from it.

4.6.1 Expected outcome

This first test's goal is to find the best way to create a 15 kg icy-regolith simulant sample while learning the procedure and the equipment needed.

To reach the best homogeneity, the liquid nitrogen suspended ice particles approach from above is utilized with a targeted water ice content of 5 wt. %. Since there is no way of precisely measuring the ice mass beforehand in this approach, multiple samples are taken from the produced batch to calculate the total mass of ice put into the sample after the process is done.

4.6.2 Execution and lessons learned

First of all, the regolith simulant is dried and stored according to Section 4.4.2.1 and Section 4.4.2.2.

The water ice particles were produced in accordance to Section 3.2. The ice machine was running for exactly 300 min, which would result in 750 g of ice if calculated based on the estimated production rate of the machine.

4.6.2.1 Regolith precooling and storage:

To precool the regolith simulant, the CF tube filled with regolith simulant was placed in a large Styrofoam box with liquid nitrogen inside. During the first hours of cool down, it was observed that liquid nitrogen leaks through this box, which made an additional metal pot inside the box necessary.

To estimate the time needed to cool down the batch, the CF tube was not screwed tight to enable a temperature measurement inside for the first few hours of cooling. This data (see Figure 4-12) suggests that 24 h of cooling should be more than enough to cool down the sample. Since the tube could not be submerged completely for this test, even faster cool down times are expected in the future when all sides can be cooled equally. Starting the cooling process the day before mixing should be therefore sufficient to reach temperatures below 100K. It would be ideal to get as close to 77 K (liquid nitrogen temperature) as possible to later on reduce the amount of dust created from evaporating nitrogen gas during the mixing process.

Figure 4-11: Cool down curve measured with a Pt-1000 sensor inside the CF tube.

4.6.2.2 Mixing setup and execution:

After cooling the regolith overnight, the temperature inside was measured again to be at 106 K (see Figure 4-13). The setup for the mixing process was prepared and the equipment was precooled. The cold CF tube was then removed from the liquid nitrogen bath.

Figure 4-12: Temperature measurement in the precooled regolith simulant sample. The Pt-1000 sensor used is built into a long copper pipe to reach the centre point of the CF tube.

The initial idea was to add liquid nitrogen to the precooled regolith directly in the CF tube. Since its temperature was still too high, a lot of dust was created. This process took multiple minutes which enabled frost to accumulate on the surfaces of the CF tube and most likely on the upper layers of the regolith simulant as well. At some point, the entire tube was then emptied into a metal mixing pot, which was already precooled from a liquid nitrogen bath in an outer larger metal pot.

With this approach, most likely a lot of fine particles left the material. It would therefore be better to precool the sample even more beforehand and then add the regolith simulant directly to the metal mixing pot while quickly placing a lid on it to prevent dust from escaping. Small amounts of liquid nitrogen could be then added at a time until the regolith exhibits a muddy texture and is easy to stir. In this state, the dust evaporation is reduced drastically.

In general, not too much liquid should be added to the regolith. Since all liquid nitrogen has to boil off either during production or later in the crucible, using only as much as necessary to keep the sample cool and easy to stir is required.

Once the right texture was reached, the liquid nitrogen-ice suspension was added to the mixture. The suspended particles were poured into the sample through a precooled 1 mm sieve into the sample. Some residues were left in the Dewar and it was flushed through again with more liquid nitrogen to retrieve as much ice as possible. Here, it might be better to only add some ice at a time and then stir the sample each time. Additionally, the ice should be stirred inside the Dewar to ensure all particles are nicely distributed in liquid nitrogen.

The icy material was then stirred for multiple minutes. During this process some larger pieces of ice were visible which were created most likely by frost falling inside the mixing pot from the CF tube during the regolith insertion and by frost build-up on the edges of the mixing pot. The two-pot setup was not able to create a dry-enough atmosphere. For future approaches, the mixing pot should be placed in a more enclosed environment, for example directly inside the large Styrofoam box used to precool the CF tube.

4.6.2.3 Taking samples to evaluate the water content:

Even before the regolith simulant was removed from the CF tube, 3 samples of approximately 20 g were taken to evaluate whether frost formed on the regolith simulant during the prolonged stay in a non-dry atmosphere (see Figure 4-14).

Figure 4-13: Small sample (approx. 20 g) taken from the precooled regolith. Some frost can be seen on the rim of the CF tube.

More samples of different sizes were taken from the later mixed icy-regolith simulant batch. Each sample was then placed in a dry environment until the liquid nitrogen inside boiled off.

The now dry appearing samples were weighed and afterwards placed in an oven at 110°C over the span of multiple days and weighed again afterwards to calculate the water content. The results are shown in Figure 4-15.

Figure 4-14: Water contents of oven-dried samples taken from the large batch. Samples 1-3 were taken before adding any ice, samples 7-10, L1, L2, T1 and T2 were taken from the icy material.

The water content measured within the first 3 samples (approximately 20 g) reflects the frost formation on the surface of the open CF tube. The samples were mostly taken from the upper few centimetres of material

that were exposed to a non-dry atmosphere. In the lower regions, less frost should be present. This frost should be minimized in future approaches by keeping the CF tube in a dry atmosphere at all times.

The samples taken from the mixed icy-regolith simulant were in the order of 20 g of mass (samples 7-10), 300 g (L1 and L2) and 5 kg of mass (T1 and T2). While the water content of most of these samples is in a similar range, sample 10 exhibited a drastically different water content of 3.3 wt. %, which could be explained due to one or more of the frost chunks being inside this small weight sample, drastically influencing the relative mass loss during drying. For this reason, the average water content of the produced batch was calculated as an average of samples 7-9, L1, L2, T1 and T2 with an ice content of 2.00 ± 0.22 wt. %.

If chunks are present, the smaller sample sizes are not reliable enough to evaluate the average water content of the entire batch and larger samples or many small samples for better statistics are needed. For homogeneous mixtures with particles in the micrometre regime, the small samples are sufficiently homogeneous to be used as ice-content estimations.

4.6.2.4 Total mass of water and conclusion:

Extrapolating the previously found water ice content to the entire batch, which consisted of 14.98 kg of dried regolith, the total water mass in the mixture was derived to be approximately $305 \text{ g} \pm 33 \text{ g}$, differing by more than a factor of two from the initially planned amount of 750 g to reach a 5 wt. % sample. This deviation reflects the uncertainty in the production rate of the ice machine as well as the losses that occur when sieving the produced ice. Additionally, frost formation inside the mixing pot during the processing could shift the here found water content even lower.

Regarding the extraction experiments, it is, therefore, reasonable to start with the dry-mix icy-regolith simulant with desiccated water ice to measure the efficiency of the system by analysing the exact mass of water ice put into the crucible and the exact mass of liquid water extracted afterwards.

The above-described production method with a more homogeneous mixture can then be used in later experiments to evaluate if there are any differences in extraction efficiency due to the form of the ice inside the sample.

4.7 Large batch production test - dry mixing

As described in the conclusion of the previous section, the wet mixing (submerged in LN₂), caused a large uncertainty in the amount of ice in the icy-regolith simulant sample. Hence, to better control the amount of ice in the sample, the decision was made to mix the ice in dry, but cooled regolith simulant. This means that the ice particles need to be desiccated first, as they are produced inside a bath of LN₂. The mass of these desiccated ice particles can then be measured before they are added to the simulant and mixed, making it possible to accurately know the ice content.

4.7.1 Regolith precooling and storage:

Precooling and storage of the regolith were carried out as described in the wet mixing procedure. To prevent leaking from the Styrofoam box due to the weight of the liquid nitrogen, a 50L stainless steel pot was placed

inside it and the CF storage tube with the regolith was placed inside the pot resting in the box, which are shown in Figure 4-16.

4.7.2 Mixing setup and execution.

After precooling of the regolith overnight, it reached temperatures below -180°C . The material needed for

Figure 4-15: Equipment for regolith precooling and storage.

mixing was gathered and precooled in the smaller Styrofoam boxes. Once everything was set and precooled, the Styrofoam was brought outside of the lab in order to prevent dust accumulation indoors. Both the stainless-steel pot and CF tube are taken outside of the box and another stainless-steel pot is placed inside the later, in order to perform the mixing inside the dry atmosphere inside the Styrofoam box.

Then, using scoops and a scale, approximately 1kg of regolith was placed inside the metal pot at a time, followed by the ice. Depending on the desired ice percentage in the mixture, these steps are repeated, making sure all tools are precooled before every scoop. The mixture of regolith and desiccated ice is shown in Figure 4-17, as well as the desiccated ice grains.

Figure 4-16: Icy regolith sample (approximately 20% ice content) and desiccated ice.

Figure 4-17: Icy regolith simulant after mixture (20% ice content).

4.7.3 Taking samples to evaluate the water content.

After mixing, once more, samples were taken to check the water content in the sample and to see whether the sample was mixed homogeneously. In the first attempt with this mixing method, a rather high ice percentage of 20% was chosen so that the sample could also be used for a preliminary experiment of extraction and capturing. Since the added ice content is known beforehand, these measurements provide a more accurate insight into the mixture’s homogeneity. In opposition to the wet mixing procedure, there is no need to wait to weigh the mixture to allow for residual liquid nitrogen to boil off. Specifically, 4001 grams of regolith simulant and 1001 grams of ice were mixed together, resulting in a mixture of just over 20%.

Figure 4-18: Water content from samples taken after mixing via dry method.

The results in Figure 4-19 indicate that there is still some heterogeneity in the sample. This is believed to come from the fact that the mixing procedure was performed by hand as no other methods were present. The results also show that the three samples have a water percentage lower than 20%; yet, considering the upper end of the error bar, the value comes close.

4.7.4 Total mass of water and conclusion:

The dry mixing method allows for much greater control of the ice in the sample, and a higher accuracy. The precision with dry mixing seems to be lower, but still within reasonable bounds. For the full-scale experiments, the dry mixing method shall be used, so that the captured water can be compared to the water input, and an estimate of the extraction efficiency can be determined.

Once enough experimental results are obtained, as an optional parameter to vary, the mixing method could be further investigated, to see whether it influences the extraction process. This would only be investigated if sufficient time is left.

4.8 Handling of the Simulant in and around the L-chamber

Once the sample is produced and ready, the filling process can begin. The crucible and the filling tube need to be cooled using liquid nitrogen before the process can start, so as not to heat the icy-regolith simulant before the extraction experiment begins. Since the sample will be exposed to the atmosphere during the filling, it is paramount that the filling process is done as fast as possible, to limit exposure. As with the other steps in the icy-regolith procedure, the tools that the sample comes into contact with are all cooled in liquid nitrogen.

The mixture of ice and regolith is transported next to the vacuum chamber, inside the large Styrofoam box and mixing pot. The Styrofoam box is filled with liquid nitrogen to maintain a cold temperature and prevent moisture to deposit in the sample.

A pre-cooled funnel and an extension tube are inserted into the filling tube of the vacuum chamber, to facilitate the filling process. Then, a pre-cooled stainless-steel jar is filled with the icy regolith and by using a pre-cooled spoon, the mixture is inserted into the crucible through the filling tube as shown in Figure 4-20. Another jar is being pre-cooled and handed to the person performing the filling once the first jar is empty. After two cups, the funnel and tube are replaced by another pre-cooled set. The funnel can heat up over time, and this causes the ice in the sample to melt creating a muddy consistency in the sample that has the potential to clog the filling tube. By frequently changing them and cooling them again this is prevented.

In between the filling process, the endoscope camera is also used to look deep into the filling tube and into the crucible to check that everything is going as planned.

Figure 4-19: Researcher feeds the icy-regolith mixture to the filling tube.

Once all regolith has been fed to the crucible, the filling tube is closed and the nominal operations to perform the experiments commence.

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Appendix

LHS-1 Lunar Highlands Simulant

For the small batch testing, the commercially available lunar regolith simulant LHS-1 by Exolith Lab was used. The properties of this simulant are listed in the following tables in comparison to the simulant made by Lunex Technologies already described in Section 4.4.1. The chemical composition is quite similar. LHS-1 has a slightly larger bulk density, which suggests that more of the smallest particles exist in comparison to the Lunex simulant that fill up the space between the larger particles.

Table 3: LHS-1 geotechnical properties in comparison to the Lunex simulant

Property	Unit	Lunex	LHS-1
Median Particle Size	µm	61	60
Particle Size Range	µm	<10 - 1000	<0.04 - 1000
Uncompressed Bulk Density	g/cm ³	1.24	1.3
Grain Density	g/cm ³	2.77	2.75
Porosity	%	N/A	52.7
Angle of Repose	°	39	47.5

Table 4: LHS-1 chemical composition as oxide sum compared to Lunex simulant

Component	Weight % Lunex	Weight % LHS-1
SiO ₂	48.7	51.2
TiO ₂	0.7	0.6
Al ₂ O ₃	26.1	26.6
FeO	3.3	2.7
MgO	2.6	1.6
CaO	13.0	12.8
Na ₂ O	3.2	2.9
K ₂ O	0.6	0.5
MnO	0.1	0.1
Cr ₂ O ₃	< 0.1	N/A
P ₂ O ₅	0.1	0.1

Table 5: Lunex regolith simulant mineral composition in Vol. % compared to LHS-1 in Wt. %

Lunex		LHS-1	
Mineral phase	Vol %	Mineralogy	Wt. %
Plagioclase feldspar (Labradorite)	9.6		
Plagioclase feldspar (Bytownite)	72.75	Anorthosite	74.4
Pyroxene (Augite)	10.48	Pyroxene	0.3
Olivine (Forsterite)	4.6	Olivine	0.2
Titanomagnetite	0.25		
Alkali Feldspar	0.08		
		Glass-rich basalt	24.7